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Synthesis of polyaniline films: case study on post gamma irradiation dose

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Abstract

The effect of gamma irradiation dose in the range of 1–10 kGy is investigated on the structural, optical and electrical properties of the polyaniline -emeraldine salt (PANI-ES) thin films deposited on the indium tin oxide (ITO) coated glass substrate by spin coating technique. X-ray diffraction patterns show that all deposited PANI films have an amorphous character. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) confirms the emeraldine salt form of deposited PANI films. The analysis of UV–Vis spectrophotometer indicates a decrease of transmittance intensity and optical band gap with increase of gamma irradiation dose while Urbach energy increases. The photoluminescence (PL) spectra show a strong peak at 429 nm due to transition from polaron band to π band in PANI structure which its intensity and peak area increase with irradiation dose increase. Electrical measurement shows that the resistivity of prepared films linearly increases with rise of gamma dose suggesting its possible application as gamma dosimeter in the studied range.